

Elite Conflict On Power Contestation Of Internal Political Party

Rasid Pora, Abdul Halil Hi. Ibrahim, Bakri Lasuhu, Rahmat Suaib

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to analyze, identify and explain, how far are the elite interests in the regional leadership council (DPW) of Partai Amanat Nasional (PAN) of North Maluku in power contestation of an internal party, and to find some factors causes that conflict. The method used is descriptive qualitative by using case studies which means that the research was done intensively, thoroughly, and deeply to an organization, institution, or certain phenomena. The data collection techniques used are observation techniques that observe the objective conditions in the field, interviewing actors involved in internal elites conflict and documentation. The results show that first, the varied pull of interests (regional election, legislative election, and presidential election) near ahead turnover of DPW PAN North Maluku is the starting point for the birth embryonic body of party internal conflict. Second, the conflict cause is a result of strengthening pragmatism attitudes of the party elite, such as the race for leadership, the utilization of caretaker position, as well as non-compliance towards party's norms and the intervention of central council of DPP PAN in process. Third, a logical consequence of open internal conflict is the exodus of thousands of party cadres (including such potential cadres) to another party. DPW PAN North Maluku failed again in North Maluku governor election period 2013-2018 in carrying Muhajir-Sahrin pairs candidate. It is also found that there is a weakness political accommodation for elected Chairman to lose candidate, so the party existence is eroded by stronger antipathy from many quarters, including voters or society. In that context, efforts to resolve internal conflict must be done in polite and elegant ways. The efforts of win-win solution can be carried out along as long as each side can show good obedience to norms and/or party constitution, without making it as justification for the interest and political factionalism of each side.

Index Terms: Indonesia political party, Indonesia election, democracy, constitution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Indonesia which explicitly understands the importance of a people's sovereignty and participates in democracy with its own variants [1]. Political parties are institutions that support the operation of representative democracy. As long as representative democracy is still regarded as the most plausible way to realize the good fortune of people, the existence of political parties will not be avoided. Political parties are needed for representative democracy to continue despite the subsequent development of political party existence at a critical point due to dysfunctional and malfunctional ones. So, basically a political party is an institution that is considered important in the modern democratic system. Democracy is a form or system of government in which all people intervene in giving participation and aspiration in public policy formulation through people's representatives or government mediation [2]. The presence of political parties became an important spacebar for classical political systems transformation into modern political methods.

This is because since the existence of political party the political formation changed drastically. Political parties have changed the relation between people and rulers, from those who initially disqualified the people from the political stage to the people as important actors and axis in relationship. In contemporary democracies, political parties have become the main instruments of people to compete and gain control over political institutions. Moreover, the presence of political parties has also changed of political elite circulation from closed to open circulation. With political parties, political positions that originally became a kind of privilege of certain social groups, became accessible from and by all societies regardless of social class and stratification [3]. As a political institution in a modern democratic system, political parties will certainly bring together many people with diverse interests and political competition. Political parties play a central role in maintaining the pluralism of political expression and ensuring political participation, as well as political competition [4]. Thus it is of course very vulnerable to conflicts within the political party. Political parties as well as modern organizations will always be in reality face of both conflict internally and externally, such as conflicts of different views, ideas or understandings, conflicting interests and so on, so basically conflict or division within the political parties can arise from scarcity of positions and resources. The fewer positions or resources each member or group can gain in a political organization, the sharper of conflict and competition between them to seize the position and source. Further, in any social hierarchy, there is only a limited number of social positions of real power and nothing more than one who can occupy it [5]. So basically a scarcity of power positions will lead to a conflict of interest within the party's own political organization and the mutual destruction of cadres, this is what conflicts as a dysfunctional form in which the actors involved in power struggles try to destroy each other [6]. Every institution, whether governmental, military, or political institution must have its own function and role, and one function and role of political party is conflict management, it is intended that the political party (senior and party members) have the ability to resolve internal and external conflict in accordance with the guidelines of political parties

- *Rasid Pora is Lecturer of Social Science Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara, Ternate, Indonesia*
- *Abdul Halil Ibrahim is Associate Professor of Social and Political Science Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara, Ternate, Indonesia, Email: halil.ibrahim@ymail.com*
- *Bakri Lasuhu is Lecturer of Social Science Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara, Ternate, Indonesia*
- *Rahmat Suaib is Lecturer of Social Science Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara, Ternate, Indonesia*

contained in the articles of association and bylaws. However, in reality, the function of political party conflict management can not be executed properly, and this is almost happening in all political parties. So it is almost certain that all political parties, both large and small, are never quiet of the conflicts that occur within him. Such a condition would certainly be able to cause the political party energy to be depleted only a matter that is not substantial. The conflict always appears before or after the congress or the party's conference at the central level while in regional deliberations area and others. This is a routine phenomenon that we always see in seeing the dynamics of political parties in Indonesia. An unhealthy phenomenon in democracy that emphasizes importance of conflict management for actors involved in discourse for power in order to gain highest position in political party stewardship structure. The inability of party elites to manage conflicts within their organizational scope, both before and after congress indicates that the political parties are not well-institutionalized. The National Mandate Party (PAN) as one of the political parties that was born in reform era also experienced internal conflicts of central board (DPP), before the presidential election in 2009, there was a difference of opinion between Soetrisno Bachir and Amien Rais. Amien Rais wants PAN to coalesce with the Democratic Party. Soetrisno Bachir wants the party in a coalition with Gerindra supporting Prabowo Subianto. It seems that PAN is now beginning to be hit by internal conflicts, 31 regional boards are asking to speed up party congresses that one of its agenda opts for new heads. Meanwhile, Soetrisno Bachir said he still wants to lead the party until the time of its completion in 2010 between January-April. In this era of Soetrisno Bachir's leadership, PAN seems to have been taken to become a modern party. Soetrisno Bachir seems to understand that the battlefield is among nationalists, so he tries to lure constituents outside PAN with his concept of four points of struggle line. This concept is Soetrisno Bachir's strategy that makes PAN able to keep its vote above 6% in the 2009 legislative elections. While PKB party as a fellow Islamic party experienced a decrease of votes up to 4.94%. So that's the concept of managing modern political parties with the methods and business management. The concept of reviving the party is interesting enough to observe. He said, if the party wants to be able to finance itself then PAN should want to raise entrepreneurs. If there are only ten percent of the employers' party, then that amount is enough to finance a party. Well, thus taking lessons of PKB collapse, as a result of internal conflict, PAN elites should be aware that conflicts should be avoided. If Soetrisno Bachir is given a chance for a future period, the concept is clear in order to raise and modernize PAN. However, now back again to the conditions and ambitions of the elites themselves. It seems that Soetrisno Bachir's position will try to be shaken again, even though his term has not ended. I do not know what's behind it. That is the picture of political parties in Indonesia, no matter the Nationalist party or the Islamic party, still the ambitions and interests of individuals or groups that arise. They generally do not prioritize interests of party but interests of others. Conflict and polarization of elites in central board (DPP) of PAN party continues in 3th PAN Congress held in Batam, even more heated. This can be seen with the absence of party chairman Sutrisno Bachir in the opening of Congress. This Congress is also full of nuances of conflict, Congress which originally will be done on January 8-10, 2010 forwarded to January 7-9, 2010. Portrait of DPP PAN elite conflict also

occurred within the internal scope of party at the regional level, especially DPW PAN-North Maluku at the time of regional deliberation some time ago. Internal party conflicts began to strengthen when the choice of candidates for governor of North Maluku that carried by the party that symbolizes the sun was in 2013. This condition causes competition in fight for chairmanship increasingly unavoidable, and even the conflict is covered DPW PAN-North Maluku already caught by chronic illness that is getting acute. This is because the DPW-PAN North Maluku personality/individual among party officials (Abd Rahim Fabanyo and Imran Djumadil or between Sahrin Hamid and Umar Bopeng) compete for leadership, and then there is a difference of perception so that in the end internal conflict can not be avoided. The internal conflicts occurring in DPW-PAN North Maluku were allegedly not due to differences in ideology or political vision, but more likely were the conflicting individual interests of each figure in competition for party leadership ahead of North Maluku governor election. The consequences of this endless conflict have dragged and even forced most potential cadres who occupy strategic positions within the party structure to move to another party. It is recorded that most of PAN officials in regency/city of North Maluku province moved to other parties. Based on the description above, the lack of clarity of internal conflict resolution DPW PAN North Maluku so that a bit more can affect the internal consolidation of party in North Maluku due to poor management which ultimately leads to the transfer of PAN cadres to other parties due to loss belief of some party members to this sun-like party. Given the importance of the role of DPW PAN North Maluku in response to the improvement of regional duties, obligations and responsibilities, it becomes imperative for the DPP PAN to succeed the task and work of DPW itself in order to improve the effectiveness organization in order to improve the election degree of North Maluku PAN otherwise. 085342944859

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses case method that is study done intensive, accurate, and deep against a certain organization, institution, or symptom [7]. The case in this study is elite conflicts on power contestation in internal political party (study on regional board of North Maluku PAN party). Therefore, researchers try to develop concepts and collect data that occur in the field, intensively cases study that have occurred and dig as much opinion from the parties who are considered competent with the problem under study. The approach is conduct through qualitative methods. This study method to describe, record, analyze and interpret conditions that occur in field. With this method is expected to be able to quickly and in accordance with data generated, so that researchers can know elite conflict in contestation of internal political party rulers. The study location is in North Maluku Province precisely in secretariat of DPW-PAN party of North Maluku Province, because this agency has full responsibility in developing, maintaining and able to neutralize the party's internal interest conflict, for that reason DPW PAN North Maluku should pay full attention in an effort to encourage party election and achievement of party objectives contained in party constitution. In this study using primary and secondary data sources. The primary data source is the source of data obtained directly from respondent or object studied, in line with this, the main data sources in qualitative research are words and actions, the rest is additional data such as documents and others [8]. While the secondary data source is a source of data obtained

through written documents, archives and others at agency related to the study. This secondary data is also a supporting data and this data is obtained from documents obtained directly from the field related to issues to be in carefully. Data collection is done by observation, interview, and documentation. Qualitative data analysis is done by working with data, organizing data, sorting it into manageable units, synthesizing, and finding patterns. Finding what is important and what is learned, and deciding what can be told to others [9]. Data analysis is the process of searching and arranging systematically the data obtained from interviews, observations (field notes), and documentation, by organizing data into categories, breaking into units, synthesizing, arranging into patterns, choosing which ones are important and will be studied, and make conclusions so easily understood by self and others [10].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Interest Contest of Elite Party

It cannot be denied that conflicts in every political event are always rooted in power struggles, therefore power is a key word to look beyond sources of conflict. Moreover, the way to understand the complexity of power in every political event must also be seen from various dimensions, both material, psychological, social contested by people involved in it. The problems point in every political event originated from claims for support and truth claims believed by each party. In addition, the dominance of a particular group over public sphere, thus narrowing space of others to give political articulation to audiences will lead to political jealousy, which in turn leads to conflict of interest between groups and individuals. Political parties in general have same goal that is to fight for interests and welfare of people in general. Because of social mandate that constituents have given in period of their birth history and at every election necessarily requires political party to side with interests of people. The noble purpose of populist value is sometimes reduced and become simplistic, what else political party is preoccupied with their internal conflicts. The conditions as described above also occur in DPW PAN-North Maluku so that reviewing conflicts that occur becomes important to be explored in order to know cause. In tracing conflicts that occurred in DPW PAN-North Maluku there are at least two reasons that cause factors. Firstly, because of competition for party and second chairman, due to the dynamics of local politics ahead of North Maluku governor election. It is true that position of chairman of political party both centered and in area has always been target of all party cadres, this is because chairman position is only one temporary who wants the job so much then competition becomes a necessity and even conflict is always unavoidable. Embryos and/or potential conflicts that occurred in internal DPW-PAN of North Maluku first took place during leadership of general chairman Abdurrahim Fabanyo at the end of his leadership, Abdurrahim Fabanyo conduct region deliberations to elect a new chairman to replace his position. Regional deliberations that were originally held at the end of 2009 in Tidore City did not run smoothly because of a conflict between Imran Djumadil and Umar Bopeng in competition for top position. As a result of conflict then deliberations in pending for a while and then deliberation resumed in Amara International Hotel of South Ternate, the deliberations are re-held and it again raises competition between Imran Djumadil and Umar Bopeng, but in

the end deliberation Imran Djumadil won by acclamation because Umar Bopeng is pressured by Abdurrahim Fabanyo to step down and let Imran Djumadil lead the DPW PAN-North Maluku. But Imran Djumadil's leadership did not last long because Imran Djumadil's leadership on his two-year journey has been turbulent, this is because most of good cadres are at DPW level, DPD wants Imran Djumadil to be demoted from his post as chairman of DPW PAN-North Maluku. The leadership of Imran Djumadil is considered in management of party is not transparent and more concerned with individual and group interests rather than party interests, so it is feared will have an impact on development of the party. As a result Imran Djumadil was dropped from his post in early 2013, so DPP showed temporary officer Sahrin Hamid to fill the vacancy of chairmanship and was given three months by DPP to carry out incredible regional deliberations (*Muswillub*) in order to elect a definitive chairman. Sahrin Hamid, who is also one of deputy chairmen of DPP, extended his decree to maintain its leadership until the end of Imran Djumadil's period in 2015. However, due to harsh protests launched by most of cadres, especially senior cadres so that in year 2013 precisely on January 25, Sahrin Hamid was forced to carry out *Muswillub* in Morotai Island Regency to elect a definitive chairman, but again *Muswillub* conducted in Morotai Island District ended with conflict between fellow cadres because *Muswillub* is considered to violate party constitution.

Cross Interest of Cadres

Interest conflicts of cadres become a distinct trend in every hustle and dynamics of political parties life. Many variants arise as a consequence of interest polarization, until cause of party dynamics become trapped in personal or group settings. The logical consequence of interest conflicts of these cadres makes political parties increasingly plowed and no longer performs their political functions as they have been known; namely as a medium of communication, aggregation, articulation, and political education. Cross phenomenon (attraction) interest of cadre become initial axis for fragility of PAN Party in North Maluku Province. Factually, the internal party factions can be read through consolidation ahead of *Muswillub* PAN which is constitutionally interpreted differently by each faction. First; *Muswillub* held in Morotai Island Regency on January 25, 2013 which resulted in Sahrin Hamid, but was rejected by the Umar Bopeng stronghold because it was considered to violate the party's Articles of Association (AD/ART). Second; *Muswillub* held in Ternate in March 2013 which immediately taken over by DPP PAN at the same time canceled the *Muswillub* results in Morotai. The above room made the party cadres internally maneuver against the DPP PAN's reaction, but it still did not result in an agreement in order to re-unify any differences and polarization of the PAN cadre's interests in North Maluku. One of the most prominent reactions after the DPP PAN attitude was strengthening of factions and/or camps that felt disadvantaged. Aggrieved cadres have view that DPP PAN's stance is also not based on constitutional considerations (in line with AD/ART), even judged to favor the camp of Sahrin Hamid. The interests of cadre that colored conflict of PAN party in North Maluku Province shows that, the phase of open conflict between local political interests and security efforts against national political momentum is presidential election, where Hatta Rajasa (as Chairman of DPP PAN) will run for president. The construction of cadre interest conflict has given rise to a triangular pattern,

namely between seizing party seats in region (internally) with local political momentum and utilization and/or safeguarding of national political momentum which has dragged PAN party of North Maluku Province into splits. Each faction claims to each other its truth. All potential cadres are trying to develop their political perceptions that serve as a justification for establishment of party spirit. But at the same time, there is also an ambiguous attitude, because the built political construction is for each camp to assert their position on political momentum ahead, namely North Maluku Governor Election and the election of DPR, DPD and DPRD and 2014 Presidential election. Cross interests of cadres in DPW PAN North Maluku thus is construction of cadres internally by making political issues such as election, legislative elections, and 2014 presidential elections as main basis to construct conflict that occurred. Although variations of issues such as procedural reasons (multiple positions), and others are used to support and justify it. Interest attraction is difficult to avoid. Various models and/or patterns of consolidation are carried out to strengthen bases and networks to secure their interests. Both (the stronghold of Sahrin Hamid and Umar Bopeng camp) fight discourse as a form of positioning of interest in push as manifestation represents party interests. The party existence was hijacked in order to fulfill desire of power which is pragmatic but not ideological. As a political party that brings up issues of change after fall of New Order regime (almost half of the party's founders are reformers), it is of course a conflict of interest involving potential internal cadres that could compromise the existence and survival of party in the future. This is where the cadre's cross points of interest are generated by the number of potential cadres and public sympathy of North Maluku PAN party falls to the most horrible point.

Conflict Growth

Prior to *Muswillub* process, internal conflicts have also arisen as interests of different cadres are attracted. The party stewardship period under Imran Jumadil leadership is deemed incapable of controlling polarization of the party's internal elites, since at the same time there is no connectivity of interest between those who think of party bargaining in process or local political momentum with those who only think of their personal and group interests. The polarization of party elites before *Muswillub* was held resulted in phenomenon of breaking bond which actually carried up to *Muswillub* momentum. Variants of elite interests split into two factions who will fight over the party seats in order to secure their respective interests. That the polarization of party elites can factually formulated the following patterns and trends; first, instinct to secure party interests in governor election momentum Period 2013-2018 by party cadres represented by Abdurrahim Fabanyo as frontman. The thought that; the failure of party when carrying candidate pairs in previous election (where DPW PAN of North Maluku carries Abdul Gafur-Abdurrahim Fabanyo) should be paid by securing party interests cadres back on political process of next period. This reason also used by most of party cadres to secure Imran Jumadil was elected as the party's chairman before being betrayed of joint commitment then dropped half way and replaced by Sahrin Hamid as a caretaker. Second; there is room for political maneuvering of established factions by promoting egoism of its interests. At this point the *Muswillub* momentum becomes arena to reinforce polarization line

because it involves party leaders who are considered to be supporters and embodiments of party image and accountability during this time. The space to distort each other is stronger which is reinforced by high expectations of various factions that appear ahead of *Muswillub* itself. Both of these factors become meta narrative of elite party polarization form as a product of factionalism of interest. Finally, this polarization makes party interests reduced as part of personal justification and group desires. The polarization also marks a new phase of internal party conflict that spawned many political risks to party sustainability. The peak is very clearly seen in the *Muswillub* that was held as well as accompanying phenomenon. The occurrence of events such as departure of cadres and party factions becomes apparent are internal political facts that are difficult to avoid.

PAN Party Dynamics Ahead of Governor Election of North Maluku

Generally, local political conditions ahead of North Maluku governor election are adorned by political claims and communication efforts against party leaders who are considered to have a strong effect on voter political support. The same conditions also occur internally, where the position of DPW PAN North Maluku which is considered sexy can be a space to lobby with other candidates to join. Toward the North Maluku Governor election, DPW PAN North Maluku as a political party that contributed four seats or his representative in North Maluku Provincial parliamentary, it will certainly be a magnet for each candidate who wants to get political support from various parties. From the beginning, the DPW PAN of North Maluku is expected to re-nominate its own party cadres and most likely option for it is only in figure of Abdurrahim Fabanyo. Mainstream is quite evenly among party cadres, because figure of Abdurrahim Fabanyo is considered to represent party interests in general, is also very big opportunity compared with other cadres. This dynamics changed, along with the journey of party management under the leadership of Imran Jumadil (originally fully supported by DPW PAN frontman), precisely because it is considered not committed then removed in the middle of the road. This is the first polarization and party conflict that emerged as a result of different views and interests in measuring momentum of North Maluku governor election period 2013-2018. The internally party dynamics become unhealthy and split. On one side; Abdurrahim Fabanyo as a regional coordinator (*Korwil*) who was given a constitutional authority to exercise control over party dynamics in his duty area, tried to exploit his political opportunities and political position in order to momentum target of North Maluku governor election, but at the same time, this commitment was injured by Imran Jumadil's already not in line with previous consensus. Imran Jumadil on the way is considered not serious in securing those interests, even assessed endanger expectations of cadres who are committed to pushing back Abdurrahim Fabanyo as North Maluku Governor Candidate. In the midst of this endless chaos, party dynamics is transformed into a mutual extermination space, even for the reason of removing Imran Jumadil from party's chairman also followed by other normative reasons such as managerial skills, as well as inadequate organizational consolidation. In fact, substantially; these opinions are merely camouflage to gain legitimacy from various stakeholders of the party in regency/city.

Triggers and Escalations

In order to save party from prolonged internal conflict and vacancy of party leadership, the urge to deploy *Muswillub* to the caretaker was inevitable. This is considered reasonable, because the normative implementation of *Muswillub* as mandated given has a time limit of up to three months. Differences of various interest internal factions party in opinion of this writer that allows opening of bargaining space Sahrin Hamid as a caretaker to affirm his political position. These efforts also find space and legitimacy. As a caretaker, Sahrin Hamid tries to use *Muswillub* space as an arena of contestation of his political interests polished in such a way as to build sympathy and empathy to all party stakeholders. Variations of interest are multi interpretation this, making cadres lose grip to whom choice was dropped through battle arena at *Muswillub*. The occurrence of miss communication among party cadres is as a result of strengthening political faction generated through classification momentary interests. The cadres also choose not to take risks for sake future and continuity their existence as politicians who certainly have instincts, feelings and political counts. As a result, mass exodus of party cadres is a form of assertiveness over political faction formed by caretaker and basic political egoism possessed by Umar Bopeng faction makes the *Muswillub's* dynamics become inconsistent with party's constitution breath. In short, *Muswillub's* dynamics are colored by phenomenon of *homo homini lupus* which ends tragically for building and future party. The embryonic conflicts and extraordinary deliberative (*Muswillub*) dynamics that took place in Morotai and Ternate City left a very sharp disparity opinion and interest, not only for internal political elite of North Maluku PAN party, but these differences interest also spread to members and/or cadres and sympathizers party at bottom even though. Cadre who feel no longer agree with the result of *Muswillub* held in Ternate then together choose to leave to another party. Moving potential cadres (said to be potential because in addition to a long time in party, some of them a party declarator had occupied structural positions, even a member of parliament active and inactive), indicating that there is a interest conflict aspect which is quite real in coloring internal party political vortex. To facilitate analysis and discussion of cadres who leave to other parties, the authors will divide this discussion into two parts, namely; the cadres who are in stewardship level DPW and cadres who come from management level DPD. The conflict that struck North Maluku DPW-PAN took a long tail, after *Muswillub* held in Ternate City was completed and won by Sahrin Hamid many party cadres and board members of DPW who declared themselves withdraw from their position as well as from PAN and moved to other party. Potential cadres of parties who move to other parties, especially the National Democratic Party (Nasdem) is not without reason, they argue that PAN Party no longer run in accordance with ideals reform as long as it is in struggle.

Post Conflict

Each conflict must have many consequences, including political party life. Many things deserve to be reformulated in order to guarantee party sustainability in the future. Starting from internal aspect as well as how to formulate a more meaningful relationship with external life. The restructuring organization is a reorganization of post-*Muswillub* party. This effort is intended to break down any strands post-conflict problems in DPW PAN North Maluku. Conflict spaces are

minimized in such a way as to maintain spirit purity of reform and creation internal political order that is obedient party norm. Factually, the post Sahrin Hamid elected party arrangement actually substantially shows symptoms that differ from their general expectations. Ideally reorganization internally party should still be done based on party play followed by arrangement of party management composition by considering accommodation aspect of various components that from beginning differ from aspect of interest. There must be ability to reunite each faction to be able to merge and reunite. Of course, more skillful and accommodative political communication is required to re-unify any differences in cadres interests, yet it is unfortunate that these efforts are not made by those elected to accommodate losers in party power struggle, whereas they are militant party cadres and has a high enough potential to gain greater PAN votes at any future political momentum. Consolidation generated parties by unilateral and non-rooted consensus will potentially harm future of party, both from legitimacy and sympathy of the voters who in fact also follow the true processes and dynamics in internal DPW PAN ahead of succession party leadership some time ago. By using narrow power logic, it is not impossible that this party will be eroded by any local political vortex as a result declining power empathy for each problem it respects.

Factors Causing Conflict

Conceptually, conflicts arise from mismatches of view and behavior. Each issue is constructed to reinforce party interests. The greatest tendencies often encountered in any vortex conflicts, including political parties are desire for power as primary goal creating and managing conflict. Political parties as a modern organization will always be faced with conflict reality, in form of differences views or ideas or understandings, conflict of interests and so on. Conflict within political parties bodies often occurs through various internal and external momentum. One of them is when succession leadership held for party leadership chair. There are generally two competing groups, the group that wants to maintain status quo and the group who want to seize domination of power that is underway. The interest in fighting over party seats was adorned by protest efforts by Umar Bopeng to DPP after being declared defeated at *Muswillub* in Morotai. The conflict DPW PAN North Maluku is colored by strengthening arguments about the violation party mechanism, so that the dispute over who is considered constitutional becomes inevitable. In the midst of this condition, option to drag DPP PAN becomes important. However, the next problem faced is how to explain this. Through a collective agreement, a stronghold who feels process *Muswillub* Morotai constitutional defect filed a lawsuit or direct protest to party headquarters. Conflicts that hit DPW PAN North Maluku actually cannot escape from attraction greater interest ahead the national political momentum, namely *Pileg* and *Pilpres* 2014. Still considered reasonable in context politics today. This means that it is necessary to support and base politics in support politics interests, so that safeguarding all resources, including network organizational is necessary. In that context, internal interest conflict within party no longer serves executor of General Chairman's duties and his factions, but already involves DPP PAN as a legitimacy space for two parties that is *vis a vis* risking all his political power. The policy to present executor of chairman task by DPP PAN in fact is a constitutional step that cannot be

avoided. Because, after removal Imran Jumadil as party leader, there is no option for DPP PAN apart from replacing party vacancy chairman in order to keep wheels and party mechanism to perform its organizational work. Attracts precisely occurred after assignment executive chair assigned to Sahrin Hamid. The approach used by DPP PAN is actually a common reason/approach applied in any organization or party, that is how far understanding and proximity of him with area because it is believed figure is able to unify any internal differences in party. This expectation did not yield anything meaningful for cadre compliance with internal consolidation process. Initially, presence of Sahrin Hamid as executor task of General Chairman of North Maluku DPW received well. However, in the process there is another maneuver, causing an inevitable internal conflict. The chairman's executive cohesion shows existence of multiple targets that were not legitimately readable by party ranks internally, even deliberately attempted by Sahrin Hamid camp, as they read greater political opportunities to solidify their positions. No half-hearted, faction is lobbying and communicating to ranks higher parties to gain legitimacy. Sahrin Hamid personally uses his position as chief executive to shed his political position. This is not without reason, that as newcomers are required to be more skilled at reading opportunities and trends that occur, both internal and external. Trying to calculate right steps and embrace all party political power internally is a choice to be taken quickly. Personally, Sahrin Hamid as party's chairman after being given authority by DPP PAN to consolidate organization in preparation for *Muswillub* in the middle of the road was changed because it was supported by local political situation which enabled him to change choice of political consolidation. The facts show that; there are alternative targets selected by Chief Executive Officer in line with momentum of North Maluku Governor election for 2013-2018 which for his personal communication and consolidation succeeded in getting one of governor candidates to pair with him. This is one of political opportunities which in his personal political instincts can not be passed, even in calculations of political mathematics, the Muhadjir-Sahrin pair predicted from beginning only to become a supplementary candidate and it seemed impossible to win political contestation. In that context, the real interest of Sahrin Hamid as executor General Chairman's job is to try and utilize governor's election space as a free socialization event for sake of his candidacy in legislative election (DPR-RI) in 2014. That personally, as a politician; he did not want to lose momentum, because time limit between election of Governor held in North Maluku with momentum of legislative election is very close. In the size political marketing, Sahrin Hamid's interests cohesion as a caretaker is greatly benefited in order to boost his election and popularity without having to spend energy and expensive costs. The problem then is; tendency to gain personal political position precisely resulted in party's image at stake. Communication space of party cadres to be cut off. The party space was buzzing by its massive phenomenon of self-congealing personal cohesion of chairman, followed by strengthening factions rejection or other camps who considered Sahrin Hamid to tap into his position to fulfill his personal and group interests. Economic powers and interests are like two sides of a coherent currency and support each other. The conflict occurred because importance of fulfilling contested economic desires. Economic factors became fastest trigger in conflict until each individual was dragged into a

sharper spiral of conflict. For that reason, the power mastery of political parties becomes necessary for certain elites to smooth their economic interests. The most commonly used party elite behavior is utilizing its political power to build its economic and business networks. Economic interests in conflict vortex of DPW PAN North Maluku since beginning according to author's analysis have been made as part of personal target or elites in conflict. Each party actually implicitly also manages political party space as an instrument to attract its business interests. Through the mastery of leadership in party, each camp ensures that there will be interest transactions with various parties. The party elite tries to negotiate its power position with business network it wants to work on. They freely manage their political position to do business consensus generated through the mechanism of political-economic bargaining. Political practice was dragged into the form of cartelization between elite who ruled over his power in political parties with economic conglomerate and business he was aiming for.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Pull of varied interests ahead chairman change of DPW PAN North Maluku is the starting point of the embryo internal party conflict. The party elite fights with all resources it has in order to manage empty space in order to assert its political position in the party. The advent of local political market ahead election of North Maluku Governor Period 2013-2018, make party *Muswillub* more sexy and loved by every party elite who want to fight. The logical consequence is unacceptable, namely; strengthening polarization interests of party elites who drag *Muswillub* space as an arena to attack each other and finish politically. Conflict that was born in internal DPW PAN North Maluku seemed to find justification space when pull interests of election and other interests is bumped with cadre's expectations of compliance with norm of party. This contradiction necessitates existence of political grouping phenomena. Open conflicts that hit DPW PAN North Maluku ahead of *Muswillub* cannot be circumvented anymore. The emergence of two opposing camps (Sahrin Hamid and Umar Bopeng) with different logic and political arguments. Factually, the emergence of faction was caused by symptom of utilizing caretaker's political position given to Sahrin Hamid when appointed by DPP-PAN replacing Imran Jumadil. The main cause of conflict in DPW-PAN North Maluku is part of strengthening triangle interest followed by the practice of seizing party chair and non-compliance with party norms and strengthening caretaker interests cohesion. In addition, the interest in party seats is believed to be an important asset for negotiating business interests of party elites. Symptoms of cartelization between politics and business also contribute to elite party to fight to fill the void of party power.

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